

Learning from conditionals: Updating by Jeffrey conditionalization

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An agent who learns the indicative conditional 'If A , then B .' should update her credences. It has recently been proposed that independent to whether the conditional strict or non-strict, the agent should update by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$ (c. f. Lipp 2022). In this note we provide the proof that Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$ is rigid and that $\neg A \vee B$ is atomic which are both necessary conditions for the application of Jeffrey conditionalization.

1 Rigidity

Let A and B be propositional variables (in italic script). The propositional variable A attains the values A and $\neg A$ (in roman script) and the propositional variable B attains the values B and $\neg B$ (in roman script). Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over the propositional variables A and B and

$$P(Z) > 0 \quad \text{for all } Z \in \{A \wedge B, A \wedge \neg B, \neg A \wedge B, \neg A \wedge \neg B\} \quad (1)$$

$$Q(Z) > 0 \quad \text{for all } Z \in \{A \wedge B, A \wedge \neg B, \neg A \wedge B, \neg A \wedge \neg B\} \quad (2)$$

We interpret P as the a priori credences of an agent and Q as the a posteriori credences of the agent after learning the indicative conditional 'If A , then B .' and updating by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$.

The probability distribution Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$ iff

$$Q(\cdot) = P(\cdot | \neg A \vee B) Q(\neg A \vee B) + P(\cdot | \neg(\neg A \vee B)) Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \quad (3)$$

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We call the update rigid iff

$$Q(\cdot|\neg A \vee B) = P(\cdot|\neg A \vee B) \quad (4a)$$

$$Q(\cdot|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) = P(\cdot|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \quad (4b)$$

c. f. Jeffrey 1983, p. 169.

The following proposition shows that eqs. (4) are fulfilled if Q is obtained by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$ and that some additional rigidity results hold.

Proposition 1. *Ridigity of Jeffrey conditionalization.* *Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . If P satisfies eq. (1), if Q satisfies eq. (2) and if Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$ (see eq. (3)), then*

$$\begin{aligned} Q(X|A \wedge B) &= P(X|A \wedge B) \\ Q(X|A \wedge \neg B) &= P(X|A \wedge \neg B) \\ Q(X|\neg A \wedge B) &= P(X|\neg A \wedge B) \\ Q(X|\neg A \wedge \neg B) &= P(X|\neg A \wedge \neg B) \\ Q(X|\neg A) &= P(X|\neg A) \\ Q(X|B) &= P(X|B) \\ Q(X|\neg A \vee B) &= P(X|\neg A \vee B) \end{aligned}$$

for any propositional variable X .

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.1.

The next proposition shows that rigidity as defined by eqs. (4) and Jeffrey conditionalization is equivalent.

Proposition 2. *Equivalence.* *Let P and Q denote probability distributions which are defined over propositional variables A and B . Let P and Q be such that P satisfies eq. (1) and Q satisfies eq. (2).*

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$$\begin{aligned} Q(X|\neg A \vee B) &= P(X|\neg A \vee B) \\ Q(X|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) &= P(X|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \end{aligned}$$

for any propositional variable X , then Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$.

The proof of the proposition is given in section A.2.

2 Atomicity

Atomicity is a notion which is discussed by Jeffrey in the context of simultaneous learning, c. f. Jeffrey 1983, p. 172-174. If an agent learns simultaneously N propositions B_1, \dots, B_N , then she has to determine the atoms and conditionalize on the atoms to derive her a posteriori credences. The atoms are the conjunctions of the propositions and their negations, i. e.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_1 &:= B_1 \wedge B_2 \wedge \dots \wedge B_{N-1} \wedge B_N \\
 A_2 &:= B_1 \wedge B_2 \wedge \dots \wedge B_{N-1} \wedge \neg B_N \\
 A_3 &:= B_1 \wedge B_2 \wedge \dots \wedge \neg B_{N-1} \wedge B_N \\
 A_4 &:= B_1 \wedge B_2 \wedge \dots \wedge \neg B_{N-1} \wedge \neg B_N \\
 &\quad \vdots \\
 A_M &:= \neg B_1 \wedge \neg B_2 \wedge \dots \wedge \neg B_{N-1} \wedge \neg B_N
 \end{aligned}$$

where $M = 2^N$

If P and Q are probability distributions which are defined over the propositional variables B_1, \dots, B_N and if A_1, \dots, A_M are such that $P(A_i) > 0$ for $i = 1, \dots, M$, then Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalization iff

$$Q(X) = \sum_{i=1}^M P(X|A_i) Q(A_i) \quad (7)$$

for any propositional variable X with $P(X) > 0$.

In the simple case, if the agent just learns one proposition, i. e. $N = 1$, then the atoms are $A_1 = B_1$ and $A_2 = \neg B_1$. In this case Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalization on B_1 iff Q satisfies

$$Q(X) = P(X|B_1) Q(B_1) + P(X|\neg B_1) Q(\neg B_1) \quad (8)$$

Let us now return to the learning of indicative conditionals. Learning the indicative conditional 'If A , then B .' is equivalent to learning the proposition $\neg A \vee B$ (c. f. Lipp 2022). The atoms are hence $\neg A \vee B$ and $\neg(\neg A \vee B)$. According to eq. (7) resp. according to eq. (8) Jeffrey conditionalization requires to conditionalize on them, i. e.

$$Q(X) = P(X|\neg A \vee B) Q(\neg A \vee B) + P(X|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \quad (9)$$

If we compare eq. (9) with eq. (3), then we observe that we have correctly identified $\neg A \vee B$ and $\neg(\neg A \vee B)$ as atoms.

3 Concluding remark

In this note we have shown that updating by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$ after learning the indicative conditional 'If A , then B .' is indeed rigid and that $\neg A \vee B$ is indeed atomic. Hence, missing rigidity or missing atomicity is not a counter-argument against updating by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$.

A Proofs

A.1 Proof of proposition 1

Let Q be defined by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$. Note first, that eq. (3) is equivalent to

$$Q(\cdot) = c_1 \cdot P(\cdot \wedge (\neg A \vee B)) + c_2 \cdot P(\cdot \wedge (\neg(\neg A \vee B))) \quad (10)$$

where

$$c_1 = \frac{Q(\neg A \vee B)}{P(\neg A \vee B)} \quad , \quad c_2 = \frac{Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B))}{P(\neg(\neg A \vee B))}$$

The proof for the equivalence is as follows: For any propositional variable X with $P(X) > 0$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} Q(X) &= P(X|\neg A \vee B) Q(\neg A \vee B) + P(X|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \\ &= \frac{P(X \wedge (\neg A \vee B))}{P(\neg A \vee B)} Q(\neg A \vee B) + \frac{P(X \wedge (\neg(\neg A \vee B)))}{P(\neg(\neg A \vee B))} Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \\ &= \frac{Q(\neg A \vee B)}{P(\neg A \vee B)} P(X \wedge (\neg A \vee B)) + \frac{Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B))}{P(\neg(\neg A \vee B))} P(X \wedge (\neg(\neg A \vee B))) \end{aligned}$$

and identifying the factors c_1 and c_2 completes the proof.

Let Y be one of the propositional variables $A \wedge B$, $A \wedge \neg B$, $\neg A \wedge B$, $\neg A \wedge \neg B$, $\neg A$, B , $\neg A \vee B$ and let X be any propositional variable. The conditional probability $Q(X|Y)$ is defined by

$$Q(X|Y) = \frac{Q(X \wedge Y)}{Q(Y)}$$

Since Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$, replacing $Q(X \wedge Y)$ respectively $Q(Y)$ by the formula (10) yields

$$Q(X|Y) = \frac{c_1 \cdot P((X \wedge Y) \wedge (\neg A \vee B)) + c_2 \cdot P((X \wedge Y) \wedge (\neg(\neg A \vee B)))}{c_1 \cdot P(Y \wedge (\neg A \vee B)) + c_2 \cdot P(Y \wedge (\neg(\neg A \vee B)))} \quad (11)$$

If Y is one of the propositional variables $A \wedge B$, $\neg A \wedge B$, $\neg A \wedge \neg B$, $\neg A$, B , $\neg A \vee B$, note

Y is not $A \wedge \neg B$, then eq. (11) simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(X|Y) &= \frac{c_1 \cdot P((X \wedge Y) \wedge (\neg A \vee B))}{c_1 \cdot P(Y \wedge (\neg A \vee B))} \\
&= \frac{P((X \wedge Y) \wedge (\neg A \vee B))}{P(Y \wedge (\neg A \vee B))} \\
&= \frac{P(X \wedge Y)}{P(Y)} \\
&= P(X|Y)
\end{aligned}$$

If Y is the propositional variable $A \wedge \neg B$, then eq. (11) simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(X|Y) &= \frac{c_2 \cdot P((X \wedge Y) \wedge (\neg(\neg A \vee B)))}{c_2 \cdot P(Y \wedge (\neg(\neg A \vee B)))} \\
&= \frac{P((X \wedge Y) \wedge (\neg(\neg A \vee B)))}{P(Y \wedge (\neg(\neg A \vee B)))} \\
&= \frac{P(X \wedge Y)}{P(Y)} \\
&= P(X|Y)
\end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof.

A.2 Proof of proposition 2

For any propositional variable X we can make the following split:

$$Q(X) = Q(X \wedge (\neg A \vee B)) + Q(X \wedge (\neg(\neg A \vee B))) \quad (12)$$

Note, by the definition of the conditional probability

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(X \wedge (\neg A \vee B)) &= Q(X|\neg A \vee B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) \\
Q(X \wedge (\neg(\neg A \vee B))) &= Q(X|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \cdot Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B))
\end{aligned}$$

Replacing the latter in eq. (12) yields

$$Q(X) = Q(X|\neg A \vee B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) + Q(X|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \cdot Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \quad (13)$$

If

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(X|A \wedge \neg B) &= P(X|A \wedge \neg B) \\
Q(X|\neg A \vee B) &= P(X|\neg A \vee B)
\end{aligned}$$

then eq. (13) yields

$$Q(X) = P(X|\neg A \vee B) \cdot Q(\neg A \vee B) + P(X|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \cdot Q(\neg(\neg A \vee B))$$

i. e. Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$.

If Q is defined by Jeffrey conditionalization on $\neg A \vee B$, then proposition 1 yields

$$\begin{aligned} Q(X|\neg A \vee B) &= P(X|\neg A \vee B) \\ Q(X|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) &= P(X|\neg(\neg A \vee B)) \end{aligned}$$

for any propositional variable X .

References

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